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INFLUENCE OF WEATHER CONDITIONS ON DEVELOPMENT OF SEASONAL AFFECTIVE DISORDERS IN CHILDREN OF THE ADVANCED SCHOOL AGE

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Abstract: Influence of weather conditions on development of seasonal affective disorders in children of the advanced school age is defined and to investigate existence of dependence of emergence of symptoms of seasonal affective disorders at a lack of sunlight during the autumn and winter period. Reliable statistically significant correlation dependence between duration of light day and quantity of the revealed symptoms during the autumn and winter period at children of the advanced school age is revealed that allows developing further preventive measures for this disturbance of health.

Keywords: seasonal affective disorder, school students, disturbance of health, weather conditions

ВЛИЯНИЕ ПОГОДНЫХ УСЛОВИЙ НА РАЗВИТИЕ СЕЗОННЫХ АФФЕКТИВНЫХ РАССТРОЙСТВ У ДЕТЕЙ СТАРШЕГО ШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

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Аннотация: Определено влияние погодных условий на развитие сезонных аффективных расстройств у детей старшего школьного возраста, а также исследовать наличие зависимости возникновения симптомов сезонных аффективных расстройств при недостатке солнечного света в осенне-зимний

период. Выявлена достоверная статистически значимая корреляционная зависимость между продолжительностью светового дня и количеством выявляемых симптомов в осенне-зимний период у детей старшего школьного возраста, что позволяет в дальнейшем разработать профилактические меры по данному нарушению здоровья.

Ключевые слова: сезонное аффективное расстройство, школьники, нарушение здоровья, погодные условия

Relevance. Now considerably the number of children at whom at the advanced school age symptoms of developing of seasonal affective disorders (SAD) are shown increased [1-3].

The prevalence of SAD fluctuates within 1-10 %. And 4-6 % of the general population of children suffer from a «winter» depression and 10-20 % have subsyndromal manifestations of a seasonal depression. The average prevalence of SAD in a zone of a temperate climate is 3-10 % while subsyndromal SAD makes 6-20 %. Women four times bigger are subject to incidence of SAD, than the man. Average age of the beginning of seasonal affective disorder is about 23 flyings, the most vulnerable age – 15-55 years, and the risk of SAD decreases with age. According to other data, the seasonal depression develops for the first time aged after 18 years old and more often occurs in women, than in men. The indicator of prevalence of SAD at children's age is 1.7-5.5 % at children aged from 9 till 19 years [4, 5].

According to forecasts of multiple expert researches, and especially WHO data, till 25th years 21 centuries of SAD will win first place in the planet, having outstripped heart troubles in this connection the relevance of studying and development of preventive measures of this disease increases [5-8].

Purpose. To define influence of weather conditions on development of seasonal affective disorders in children of the advanced school age and also to investigate existence of dependence of emergence of symptoms of SAD at a lack of sunlight during the autumn and winter period and to check emergence of dependence on gender signs.

Materials and methods of a research. In this work were used: a method of sociological poll (by questioning with the voluntary consent of respondents), a comparative and analytical method, a method of the correlation analysis and statistical processing of the obtained data was carried out. By means of questioning and testing were the material confirming influence of weather conditions, namely a lack of sunlight, on emotional and physical conditions of the person is built. Questioning was carried out in high school of the Grodno city gymnasium. The total volume of selection was 120 people (9-11 classes) of them: 63 girls and 57 boys.

Results and their discussion. SAD are a frustration of mood, which is characterized by seasonal frequency of the main depressive episodes and arises annually approximately at the same time. There are two seasonal models of a depression: summer and winter type.

Allocate also subsyndromal SAD forms at which vegetative symptoms are clinically significant. SAD is differentiated with an atypical depression, a cyclothymia, a dysthymia and a chronic unipolar depression, which can be provided by deterioration in symptoms to wintertime. The diagnosis of SAD assumes full remission of symptoms after the end of a winter season.

The fact that sunlight well influences a human body is known long ago. The Sun radiates the curative beams on rising. By scientists it is established that the most active of all invisible parts of a range which is deeply getting into a body of the person and, in too time, the safest, is red and infrared (IR) light. Red and IR light improves function warmly – the vascular system, normalizes arterial blood pressure, stimulates breath, normalizes many indicators of blood, harmonizes a condition of an organism, restores own protective forces. Light waves raise power and a condition of the immune system. Natural waves of light regulate functions of twenty hormones, including melatonin – hormone of the pineal gland performing functions of an inner biological clock. At hit on a body of the person light waves refract, reflected, absorbed and activate various chemical and physical processes in the upper layer of the skin, cause photo-electric and photochemical effects.

The lack of sunlight during the autumn and winter period can be one of the reasons, so-called seasonal affective disorders. SAD is most widespread in areas where winter days very short or are big changes in quantity of a daylight at different times years. A considerable part of the population of northern latitudes with shortening of days of fall and winter has a syndrome complex, which can consist of a depression, fatigue, a hypersomnia, a hyperphagia, desires are carbohydrates, increases in weight and decrease in a libido. At a winter depression such symptoms as decrease in vital energy, difficulty of concentration of attention, fatigue, and requirement to spend time alone, decrease in social activity can be shown. If these symptoms are present in wintertime, decrease with lengthening of days in the spring and disappear during the summer period, seasonal affective disorder is diagnosed.

For the diagnosis of SAD it is also required that throughout the patient's life the number of seasonal depressive episodes significantly exceeded quantity of no seasonal episodes. Diagnostic criterion of SAD is existence of the main and additional symptoms (The international classification of diseases, the 10th edition – ICD-10).

SAD pathogeny, despite a large number of hypotheses, up to the end is not clear. In the light of our hypothesis of a light deprivation close attention is drawn by hormone of a pineal gland – melatonin which synthesis is in the dark

activated by noradrenergic mechanisms of a sympathetic nervous system and is synchronized by the level of external illumination through a suprachiasmatic kernel of a hypothalamus. Decrease in level or disturbance of biorhythmologic structure of synthesis of melatonin is noted at different types of a depression, including SAD. It is supposed that neurochemical SAD mechanisms, including changes of exchange of serotonin and melatonin, are connected with genetic factors.

Based on statistical processing of the obtained data of a research existence of communication between emergence of symptoms of SAD and a lack of solar impact on an organism of children of advanced age during the autumn and winter period is established. By means of the correlation analysis across Spirmen close correlation connection between duration of light day and quantity of the revealed main and additional symptoms is established. The correlation coefficient made 0.647 (at level of significance $r < 0.001$). And, at paired comparison of selections of boys and girls correlation communication at girls was shown stronger, than at boys. So, at girls it made 0.703 (at level of significance $r < 0.001$), and at boys 0.52 (at level of significance $r < 0.001$).

Conclusions. Thus, reliable statistically significant correlation dependence between duration of light day and quantity of the revealed SAD symptoms during the autumn and winter period at children of the advanced school age is revealed that allows to develop further preventive measures for this disturbance of health.

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